

ACTIVITY 2.2.2.3: COMMUNITY-LEVEL RISK REDUCTION INTERVENTIONS AT BAT GUANO HARVEST SITES IN KAMPOT AND BATTAMBANG PROVINCES

Interim Implementation Report

Investigating Behaviors Related to the Use and Adoption of Personal Protective Equipment and Hygiene Practices

A Report from STOP Spillover Cambodia

June 2024

Cover photo: Caved-bat guano harvesters with suboptimal uses of PPE in Battambang province.

Photo Credit: STOP Spillover Cambodia

STOP Spillover

Strategies to Prevent Spillover (or STOP Spillover) enhances global understanding of the complex causes of the spread of a selected group of zoonotic viruses from animals to humans. The project builds government and stakeholder capacity in priority Asian and African countries to identify, assess, and monitor risks associated with these viruses and develop and introduce proven and novel risk reduction measures. “Spillover” refers to an event in which an emerging zoonotic virus is transferred from a non-human animal host species (livestock or wildlife) to another, or to humans.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CBGHC	Caved Bat Guano Harvesting Community
GP	Good Practice
HHC	Helping Hands Concept
KAP	Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices
NECHR	National Ethics Committee for Health Research
NiV	Nipah Virus
OHDRaM WG	One Health Design Research and Mentoring Working Group
PDOE	Provincial Department of Environment
PKLFPC	Phnom Kuhear Loung Forest Protected Community
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
PRSFPC	Phnom Romsay Sak Forest Protected Community
RRI	Risk Reduction Intervention
STOP Spillover	Strategies to Prevent Spillover
USAID	United States Agency for International Development

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

From February 2024 – June 2024 the Strategies to Prevent Spillover (STOP Spillover) team implemented a number of interventions with bat guano harvesters in the Kampot and Battambang provinces of Cambodia (Annex 1). These interventions were designed to promote the adoption of risk reduction behaviors, to reduce the threat of zoonotic spillover from bats to humans. Risk reduction behaviors included the adoption of Personal Protection Equipment (PPE) such as the use of hats, gloves, goggles and dedicated clothing while harvesting or handling bat guano, and hand washing with soap after harvesting or handling bat guano. This report summarizes initial results, findings and learnings from these interventions, which involved 114 stakeholders in the two zones (Annex 2).

This interim report, focused on community-level risk reduction interventions (RRI) at bat guano harvesting sites provides valuable insights into the behaviors and practices of guano harvesters, and the effectiveness of the implemented interventions. For example, the participatory approach adopted by the project has been instrumental in identifying and addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by the guano harvesting communities while ensuring local voices are heard. By engaging community members in the design and testing of interventions, the project ensured that interventions are contextually relevant and have a higher likelihood of being sustained.

The initial commitment of the one community to adopt all proposed PPE items is commendable. However, practical challenges such as goggles fogging inside caves, highlight the need for PPE that is not only protective but also adaptable to local working conditions and to working in caves. In the second community the gradual adoption of full PPE, with the initial use of hats evolving to include masks and gloves, demonstrates the importance and the impact of sustained guidance and support. This incremental approach may serve as a model for other communities where immediate comprehensive adoption of PPE is challenging.

The positive changes observed during the intervention period, such as the consistent use of PPE and adherence to handwashing protocols, are promising indicators of intervention impacts. Significant improvement in communities' understanding of zoonotic diseases and the importance of biosafety measures, as evidenced by pre- and post-test results, underscores the value of STOP Spillover's work.

However, challenges remain. The limited participation of temporary workers and the initial reluctance of some community members to fully adopt PPE due to financial constraints highlight the need for continued support and innovative solutions to ensure widespread adoption of risk reduction practices.

As the project moves forward, it is crucial to maintain this momentum and to continue refining interventions based on feedback and experiences of community members. The endpoint consultative assessment will be a critical step in evaluating the long-term effectiveness of these interventions and in identifying areas for further improvement.

In conclusion, this interim report highlights progress made in reducing zoonotic disease transmission risks in bat guano harvesting communities. Continued engagement, monitoring, and adaptation of the interventions will be essential to ensure that the communities are equipped to sustain these risk reduction practices and protect themselves from the threat of zoonotic diseases over time. These interventions serve as a model for similar initiatives worldwide, demonstrating the importance of community involvement and tailored interventions in addressing global health challenges.

I.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In January 2024, the Strategies to Prevent Spillover (STOP Spillover) Cambodia team conducted two participatory assessments in the Phnom Romsay Sak Forest Protected Community (PRSFPC) and the Phnom Kuhear Loung Forest Protected Community (PKLFPC), located in Battambang and Kampot provinces, respectively. Using a community dialogue approach, these assessments aimed to achieve three primary objectives:

1. To gather baseline data using a Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) survey;
2. To initiate cooperative discussions on potential health issues, the impact of outbreaks, zoonotic diseases, and potential solutions; and
3. To allow community members to collaboratively create options for risk reduction interventions (RRIs) with support from a One-Health Design Research and Mentoring working group (OHDRaM WG), also referred to as the intervention co-design phase.

The baseline data collected during the participatory assessment process highlighted gaps in community knowledge of zoonotic diseases, their understanding of associated risks, and the use of preventive measures. To address these gaps, an OHDRaM WG developed and organized campaigns to enhance awareness of risks and increase adoption and use of risk reduction measures. Organizing visits to share experiences and lessons learned from established guano producers was identified as a crucial step to bridge existing knowledge and risk perception gaps.

During the co-design phase, communities identified and prioritized key RRI practices that were highly relevant to their work harvesting bat guano from caves. Among these were the wearing of fabric or surgical masks (Good Practice [GP] #1), gloves (GP#2), and the establishment of handwashing stations (GP#7). It is important to note that these practices fell into two main categories: the first being the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), and the second concerning the adoption of hygiene practices.

To further strengthen community risk awareness, it was important to negotiate and persuade committed community members to implement their chosen interventions over a specified time period. This was accompanied by the completion of reminder sheets and a regular monitoring process, including midpoint and endpoint assessments. This report describes the intervention implementation process, the monitoring procedures, and lessons learned and experiences gained by participating communities.

The participatory assessments and subsequent interventions represent a collaborative approach to community health and safety in the context of zoonotic disease prevention. By engaging directly with communities and leveraging their insights and preferences, the OHDRaM WG facilitated the development of tailored interventions that resonate with the unique needs and

challenges faced by bat guano collectors working in bat cave environments. The emphasis on practical and context-specific risk reduction practices reflects a deep understanding of the working conditions and potential hazards inherent in bat guano harvesting.

As the work progresses, experiences documented in this report will serve as a valuable resource for similar initiatives aimed at mitigating health risks in other high-risk bat-human environments. The collaborative model adopted here, which combines community engagement with expert guidance, sets a precedent for future efforts to enhance occupational health and safety in rural communities while respecting livelihoods, personal autonomy, and local knowledge. The ongoing commitment to monitoring and adapting interventions based on community feedback underscores the dynamic and responsive nature of this One Health initiative. Through continued dialogue, education, and the sharing of best practices, we aim to foster a culture of safety and resilience against a backdrop of emerging zoonotic threats.

1.2 Objectives and Research Questions

The objective of this intervention is to explore ways in which cave-associated bat guano harvesting communities can disrupt high-risk spillover pathways and protect themselves from zoonotic spillover risks. Intervention findings will highlight the determinants of actual risk reduction behaviors rather than the determinants of historical or hypothetical behaviors. This intervention will: (1) add to the information base concerning current risk avoidance behaviors at the onset of the activity; (2) inform program managers about what behaviors programs should promote, eliminate, or modify based on what people can and will do using their own resources; (3) inform the social behavior change program on the most effective motivators and most significant barriers to adopting new behaviors; and (4) indicate what kind of support may be needed and what level of change in particular behaviors the program can expect.

This intervention aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the current practices of bat guano collecting communities in relation to the prioritized risk pathways, and participant perceptions of risk for zoonotic disease? Do these vary by community characteristics?
2. What are the initial reactions from the bat guano harvesting community members to proposed modifications to their practices and which risk reduction behaviors are they willing to try?
3. What practices are participants successfully adopting and where do they adjust, drop certain aspects, or stop the practice completely? What are the reasons for adoption or non-adoption?
4. What do participants perceive to be the advantages and disadvantages of new or modified behaviors, and what support do they believe will be needed to sustain these practices?

2.0 METHODS

2.1 Program Stakeholders and Communities

Before the RRI began, foundational educational talks and presentations were conducted to address the knowledge gaps in zoonotic diseases, biosafety, and prevention identified by an initial KAP survey. This campaign included two key elements: a pair of one-hour training sessions analyzing risk pathways, outcomes, and preventive measures through pictorial scenarios, and a series of seven infographics detailing zoonoses and correct handwashing techniques, supplemented by hands-on demonstration sessions.

A total of 114 individuals participated in these sessions across both provinces. In Kampot, attendees included 13 active members of the OHDRaM WG, including three national technical officials and nine provincial-level representatives from various departments and local authorities, alongside 34 community workers involved in guano-related activities. In Battambang, 67 individuals participated, including 14 OHDRaM WG members and 53 guano harvesters. The effectiveness of these educational sessions was evaluated using pre- and post-tests to measure comprehension of the topics discussed. Results from these pre- and post-tests are presented in Section 3.

Additionally, OHDRaM WG members conducted a market survey to ascertain the availability and cost of protective gear, such as gloves, hats, face masks (both fabric and surgical), goggles (protective eye gear), and soap. Survey results, which included vendor counts, types of PPE available, contact information for sellers, and prices for each item, were disseminated among community leaders, village chiefs, and OHDRaM WG team members. This information streamlined the purchasing process and budgeting for the community.

Subsequent to the education campaign, consultative dialogues were initiated within target communities. An orientation seminar was first provided to 26 active OHDRaM WG members, covering the facilitators' guide, negotiation techniques, preliminary dialogue questionnaires, and the Helping Hands Concept (HHC). This was followed by post-training evaluations to inform future enhancements. Two HHC groups were then formed, each including three volunteer OHDRaM WG members—a local health worker, a commune council member, and a district veterinary officer. These groups were tasked with offering ongoing technical advice and support to their respective communities on the correct use of protective gear and handwashing, as well as guidance on PPE procurement, in addition to periodically monitoring RRIs.

OHDRaM WG members proceeded to lead dialogues with guano-related workers from the two protected community forests (PRSFPC and PKLFPC). These dialogues began with plenary sessions to ensure all community members were well-informed about the objectives, foundational rules, and responsibilities of each stakeholder during the implementation process.

2.2 Participant Selection Process

In the co-design phase to develop RRI, all community members, particularly those engaged in bat guano-related work, were encouraged to participate. Proposed interventions were conceived by community members themselves, with a focus on practicality and potential for success. Participation in the implementation of these interventions was not mandatory. Bat guano harvesters and community participants selected which interventions they wanted to test. There was no external assistance provided in procuring PPE and hygiene materials; individuals who committed to test these practices did so at their own expense.

Participant involvement was based on self-selection, meaning that individuals volunteered to participate and carry out the interventions they preferred. Participants willingly contributed their time, thoughts, and experience during meetings and follow-up sessions.

Participants ranged from 28–63 years of age and had worked in the industry for 10–20 years.

2.3 Intervention Kickoff, Monitoring, and Assessment

Intervention implementation was structured into three distinct phases, each with its own set of goals (referenced in Table 1). The initial phase marked the beginning of intervention implementation, focusing on finalizing the confirmed behaviors to be put into practice, combined with counseling and negotiation efforts. The second phase was dedicated to follow-up actions and a midpoint evaluation, carried out independently by OHDReM WG members. The final phase included an assessment of community responses and any changes resulting from the interventions. This final stage also reconvened all stakeholders for a closing round of consultative dialogue and collective reflection.

Table 1. Community visits during the intervention implementation period

Phase 1: Kickoff Sessions	Phase 2: Follow-up and Midpoint Check-in	Phase 3: Assess Change and Reactions
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consult and confirm with community members the co-designed RRI/practices related to risk pathways; identify gaps; • Discuss issues and solutions with each community; • Discuss risk reduction behaviors that match community needs; and • Negotiate with communities on what practices the communities will implement over a pre-determined period. 	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check in with community members to see how they are proceeding with the co-designed or modified practices; • Conduct problem-solving as needed with each community; and • Check on agreement to continue. 	<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review what happened, results, and changes in each community; and • Reflect on community experiences: advantages, disadvantages, and recommendations for others.

Phase 1: Kickoff Sessions	Phase 2: Follow-up and Midpoint Check-in	Phase 3: Assess Change and Reactions
<p>Role players:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project team of STOP Spillover Cambodia; • National and subnational OHDRaM WG members; • A cross-province OHDRaM WG member from Kampong Cham; and • Local authorities (district, communes, and villages) and community representatives. 	<p>Role players:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established groups of HHC/monitoring teams were well-trained, and this local capacity was built based on local experiences and implemented with the project team. 	<p>Role players:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The HHC/monitoring team; • National and subnational OHDRaM WG members; and • Local authorities (district, communes, and villages) and community representatives.

2.3.1 Intervention Kickoff Event

2.3.1.1 SCHEDULES OF THE IMPLEMENTATION

Establishing a period of practice was a crucial component of this intervention. The implementation schedule was collaboratively developed with community members. Each community had a three-day window to prepare for the launch of co-designed RRI and to procure necessary PPE and other materials. Following this preparatory phase, a 21-day period was allocated for the actual implementation and monitoring adoption of interventions (Figure 2).

Distinct differences emerged between the two communities, PRSFPC and PKLFPC, regarding the duration of the intervention. Variance in their harvesting cycles and leadership structures accounted for these differences. For PRSFPC, bat guano harvesting was scheduled once every 45 days. Community members engaged in bat guano collection inside the cave during four days in a two-week period, followed by three days spent changing guano sacks, sewing, and transporting the guano to a storage facility. Consequently, PRSFPC members engaged in the intervention practices for a total of seven days during the implementation period.

Conversely, PKLFPC community members had a more extended experience with the intervention. Unlike PRSFPC, PKLFPC did not adhere to a fixed harvesting cycle, allowing guano harvesters to enter the cave and collect guano daily from their assigned plots. This resulted in a longer intervention period for the PKLFPC community compared to PRSFPC.

Figure 2. Implementation schedule and plan

2.3.1.2 CONFIRMED PARTICIPANTS

Drawing from the initial roster of participants from the baseline data gathering phase, these same individuals were invited, along with their colleagues, to a joint consultation for intervention design. The project team provided an overview of the collaboratively formulated risk mitigation strategies and the commitment matrix. The matrix included the names and essential details of guano harvesters and others who expressed interest in trying the risk reduction practices.

Subsequently, attendees were organized into breakout groups. Each group was led by a three OHDRaM WG members—two tasked with engaging the group in participatory discussions and dialogue, and one assigned to document the proceedings. The composition of the breakout groups and the participant count from each province are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Numbers of breakout groups and participants

No.	PKLFPC	Number of Participants	PRSFPC	Number of Participants
1	Female guano harvesters – Group 1	12 people	Female guano harvesters – Group 1	25 people
2	Male guano harvesters – Group 2	16 people	Male guano harvesters – Group 2	28 people
3	Mixed (trader-cum-transporter) – Group 3	06 people (03 females)	None	None
	TOTAL	34 participants (15 female)		53 participants (25 female)

2.3.1.3 CONSULTATION AND NEGOTIATION

OHDRaM WG members used a consultative dialogue questionnaire (found in Annex 4) to confirm details such as existing guano harvesting methods, potential risk pathways, perceptions of zoonotic diseases, and initial responses to proposed interventions. Concurrently, they

initiated discussions on the use of PPE and hygiene practices. Given that the community was expected to utilize its own resources to enact the risk mitigation strategies, the OHDRaM WG made a concerted effort to negotiate these costs with community members. To facilitate this, a comprehensive set of questions was incorporated into the guide (Annex 4).

2.3.2 Intervention Monitoring

A monitoring team consisting of OHDRaM WG members was responsible for intervention surveillance. They utilized three tools: a reminder sheet (Figure 3), an observational checklist, and the midpoint assessment questionnaire (detailed in Annex 6). The guano harvesters individually filled out the reminder sheet to aid in the consistent application of interventions. The monitoring team completed the observational checklist. These documents were analyzed side by side to assess the uniformity of the practices adopted.

Overall, the monitoring team reviewed the extent to which community members adhered to each practice, whether they were followed and adopted consistently, completely, partially, or had modified, discontinued, or ceased implementation altogether. Additionally, they helped to understand the reasons behind these decisions.

REMEMBER!			
WASH HANDS AFTER EVERY CONTACT WITH BATS OR BAT GUANO			
YOU NEED:	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
A PLACE 			
WATER WASHING 			
DETERGENT 			
DO YOU HAVE A PLACE TO WASH HANDS WITH DETERGENT? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO ARE YOU DOING IT? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO			

Figure 3. A reminder sheet for handwashing practices

2.3.3 Endpoint Consultative Assessment

At the end of the implementation period the team went back to assess participants' experiences, focusing on three specific domains, which correspond to the three segments found in the endpoint community dialogue questionnaire (see Annex 6 for details). The initial segment aimed to gauge the community's views on the advantages and drawbacks of the risk reduction practices. This was followed by an assessment of the support systems they needed to maintain the positive outcomes resulting from the risk mitigation strategies. The concluding segment included validation questions addressing the practicality, feasibility, and impact of risk reduction measures tested by the community. Responses gathered will serve as a reference point for verification after the final assessment in fiscal year 2025.

Representatives from various groups, including OHDRaM WG members, national and local stakeholders, municipal leaders, and the project team, were convened to engage in this dialogue. Their participation facilitated the process, ensured detailed record-keeping, and provided a platform for exchanging insights and experiences.

2.4 *Data Collection, Management, and Analysis*

We used three pretested consultative dialogue questionnaires for data collection. Additionally, we utilized illustrative reminder sheets (for community members) and an observation checklist (similar to the reminder sheet but completed by the assigned monitoring team based on their actual observations). To reinforce final conclusions and recommendations, we engaged with OHDRaM WG members who served as notetakers and interviewers during the intervention period, seeking their insights on significant changes and factors influencing people's behavior. These insights are incorporated into the report's discussion and recommendations.

Intervention data was manually gathered under the guidance of the technical lead and activity co-lead. Community-specific intervention outcomes were entered into a central "master table" to facilitate analysis. Qualitative data was also summarized, including verbatim participant statements. After completing fieldwork, the research team meticulously analyzed field notes, focusing on identifying promising practices within the two interventions, as well as noting any challenges faced and ongoing support needed. These findings informed the drafting of final recommendations.

2.5 *Ethical Considerations and Approvals*

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical research principles and received approval from the National Ethics Committee for Health Research (NECHR) of Cambodia (IRB number 394 NECHR as given in Annex 7). Prior to data collection, enumerators participated in mandatory ethics and compliance training.

2.5.1 Informed Consent

The study ensured informed consent (Annex 2) from the two target communities. We emphasized the voluntary nature of participation, with the right to withdraw at any point without consequence. The research team provided a clear explanation of the study procedures, ensuring participating communities understood their involvement before providing written consent.

2.5.2 Confidentiality

To ensure participant anonymity and uphold ethical research principles, the study implemented several confidentiality measures. Consultative dialogue questionnaires and observation forms excluded any identifying information, relying solely on assigned ID numbers for reference. Participating community consent forms, however, did include names but lacked these ID numbers. These forms were then stored securely and separately from the dialogue data itself. Finally, the informed consent process, verbally explained and presented in writing, clearly outlined participants' rights to confidentiality. This included the right to refuse to answer any questions they felt uncomfortable with, the right to withdraw from the study at any time, and the assurance that declining participation would not affect their access to any services.

2.5.3 Participant Protection

The consent form also detailed all potential risks and corresponding safeguards. Additionally, participants received contact information for a local study team member whom they could contact to address any questions or concerns.

2.6 *Timeline*

In anticipation of the intervention's launch in May 2024, orientation sessions for OHDRaM WG members were organized to foster collaboration. Meetings with local authorities were held to secure their endorsement. Following United States Agency for International Development's (USAID) approval of the Participatory Assessment Report, the intervention was implemented. The intervention was structured into three principal stages: the first involved an initial consultative dialogue with each community to select the practices they would test, the second stage included a midpoint assessment to track progress and elucidate adapted practices as necessary, and the final stage entailed a comprehensive consultative dialogue to compile feedback from all participating communities. Throughout the duration of the intervention, data cleaning and initial analysis were conducted as ongoing processes, as elaborated on in Annex I.

3.0 FINDINGS

3.1 Current Practices and Risk Pathways

Multiple zoonotic disease transmission routes are linked to activities involving human contact with bats and bat guano handling within caves. These pathways include:

1. Direct contact with bats and guano by individuals harvesting bat guano;
2. Contamination of food and water sources by bat saliva, urine or guano; and
3. Inhalation of dust contaminated by bat-borne pathogens from guano.

In early 2024, the STOP Spillover team in Cambodia conducted KAP surveys among 60 bat guano collectors from two communities. The objectives were to record:

1. Their existing practices and the associated risks pertaining to these identified risk pathways; and
2. Knowledge of bat-borne diseases that could emerge along these pathways.

We found no notable differences in the perceived risk and knowledge of transmission routes between the two communities (Table 3).

Table 3. Highlights of findings from earlier studies relevant for this intervention (described in more detail in the Participatory Assessment Report in April 2024)

Risk Pathways	Survey Highlights	
	PRSFPC	PKLFPC
Direct Exposure (ex. guano collection): No use of PPE	√	√
From clothes worn during guano harvesting: No dedicated clothes, no removal of clothes after guano harvesting, no daily clothes washing	√	√
Contaminated Hands: No gloves, no handwashing	√	√
Contaminated Food and Water: Eat and drink in the cave without washing hands	√	√
Contact with Dust (surfaces of sacks): Touch and handle guano sacks with bare hands	√	√
Contact with Dead Bats: Touch dead bats	√	√

3.2 Pre- and Post-Test Results

Following the initial assessment of bat guano harvesters' knowledge of zoonotic diseases, a training and evaluation program was conducted for 87 participants during a participatory assessment event with the two target communities. Training covered the recognition of disease

symptoms, modes of transmission from animals to humans, and the crucial role of PPE in prevention. Diseases included rabies, COVID-19, histoplasmosis, and Nipah virus (NiV).

Results showed a statistically significant improvement in test scores, with an increase from an average of **58.5%** before the training to **69.5%** after the training ($p = 0.0001$). There was no correlation found between test results and the length of a participants' experience in guano collection or their specific roles in the harvesting process. Overall knowledge scores improved by **11%**. Notably, participants were least aware of the benefits of using PPE and the risks of histoplasmosis and NiV. These diseases are emerging and increasingly prevalent and can have severe implications, but they are relatively unknown in Cambodia.

The training on zoonotic diseases and biosafety proved to be an essential initiative for these community groups. Although the training achieved modest success in imparting short-term knowledge to guano collectors, a complete evaluation of its effectiveness requires observation and measurement of behavioral changes pre- and post-training. A long-term follow-up with quantifiable outcomes is essential to fully assess the impact of this initial training.

3.3 Intervention Participants

The team engaged a cohort of 40 volunteers from two communities for the pilot intervention (Table 2). Participation was mostly determined by self-selection, but it also required adherence to key criteria: direct involvement with bat guano production and willingness to adopt the proposed risk reduction behaviors. This number represented a reduction from the original group of participants recorded during the participatory assessment (see Table 4 for details). Several individuals who initially expressed interest opted out due to a range of factors.

Table 4. Participating community characteristics

	Community Characteristics	PRSFPC	PKLFPC		
	Mean age (years)	46	45		
	Gender	61% Female	86% Female		
Number of participants who initially expressed interest in the intervention	Primarily responsible for guano harvesting (guano harvester)	10 people	25 people		
	Primarily responsible for bat guano production activities or involvement in related preventive behaviors	Guano carrier	06	Guano carrier	02
		Sack seamstress	12	Trader-cum-transporter	07
		Dropper	19		
Transporter		06			
	Total	53	34		

	Community Characteristics	PRSFPC	PKLFPC											
Final number of self-selected participants in the intervention	Primarily responsible for guano harvesting (guano harvester)	10 people	10 people											
	Primarily responsible for bat guano production activities or involvement in related preventive behaviors	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Guano carrier</td> <td>06</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sack seamstress</td> <td>02</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dropper</td> <td>04</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Transporter</td> <td>04</td> </tr> </table>	Guano carrier	06	Sack seamstress	02	Dropper	04	Transporter	04	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Guano carrier</td> <td>02</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Trader-cum-transporter</td> <td>02</td> </tr> </table>	Guano carrier	02	Trader-cum-transporter
Guano carrier	06													
Sack seamstress	02													
Dropper	04													
Transporter	04													
Guano carrier	02													
Trader-cum-transporter	02													
	Total	26 people	14 people											

3.4 Participants’ Perceptions of Risk

Upon obtaining informed consent, participants were surveyed about their perceived risks from living in proximity to bats. While most acknowledged a degree of risk, a thematic analysis indicated consistent primary concerns within both the PRSFPC and PKLFPC communities. For PRSFPC’s dedicated members, they were prompted to evaluate their level of concern regarding various cave-related tasks on a scale from **1** (minimal concern) to **10** (maximum concern). The assessment of apprehensions tied to bat guano production showed that a vast majority (24 out of 26 individuals) harbored concerns or perceived risks linked to these tasks. The scope of these tasks spans the full spectrum of the production process, which includes harvesting, carrying, sewing guano sacks, and transporting bat guano. Interestingly, two participants reported no concerns and no prior incidents of bat-related infections.

“I have not personally experienced any health issues related to this work.” (A male bat guano harvester in Battambang province)

“This type of work has been done by my family and me for a long time, and we have not experienced any health problems. While I am not personally aware of the potential risks, I am not concerned about them.” (A male bat guano harvester in Battambang province)

The intensity of concerns about risk among participants differed. When asked to evaluate specific activities involved in bat guano production, most participants rated the risk between **2** and **10**, with a mean risk score of **5.6** (out of 10). The task of harvesting guano was identified as the most risky, followed by carrying and sewing guano sacks (Table 5). In contrast, transporting sacks were perceived to be less risky. It is noteworthy that only one of the 26 participants assigned a “high” risk rating (a score of **10**) due to potential health implications.

“My routine tasks involve collecting and sewing bat guano sacks, which raises concerns for me regarding contracting infectious diseases [from bats].” (A male bat guano harvester in Battambang province)

Table 5. Average level of concerns by activity rated by the committed participants

Task	Level of Concern (n=26) (1 to 10 – 1 is the least concern, 10 is the most concern)
Harvesting	7.0
Carrying	6.5
Sewing	5.0
Transporting	2.5

Participants expressing heightened concern about the tasks of harvesting, carrying, and sewing guano sacks linked their worries to the health hazards posed by exposure to bat guano dust and its associated odors.

“The strong odor associated with bat guano is a concern for me, as it may contribute to respiratory issues, including fever and cold-like symptoms.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

“Inhaling bat guano exposes me to a very unpleasant odor and dust, which irritates my nasal passages. The presence of insects in the guano is another concern.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

“While I have limited job options, I share concerns about the potential for contracting infectious diseases from bats, particularly those that might be unknown, like COVID-19.” (A female guano trader-cum-transporter in Kampot province)

“The unpleasant odor from bat guano is a concern, and I worry about its potential health effects.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

The perception of risk was notably lower for transporting guano sacks, likely due to the reduced direct interaction with bats and their waste inside the caves. The routine practice of replacing damaged sacks also plays a role in diminishing perceived risk. A considerable number of participants dealing with these tasks work with previously closed sacks, which lessens the chance of exposure.

“At least dropping off the guano sacks keeps me away from the bats and that dust. Those ripped sacks worry me though, hopefully they get replaced often.” (A male guano dropper in Battambang province)

“These pre-sealed guano sacks are a blessing! No more dust getting in my lungs or having to worry about what’s inside.” (A female guano dropper in Battambang province)

“I would not mind transporting guano sacks all day if it meant staying out of those caves.” (A female guano dropper in Battambang province)

Despite recognizing the potential health risks from bats as highlighted in their training, an intriguing contradiction was noted among participants. They referenced their long-standing experience—spanning decades—of working with guano and bats without suffering any bat-related diseases, which seemed to downplay the perceived risk.

“They say bats can spread diseases in training, but I have been working with them for years and never get sick. Makes you wonder...” (A group of bat guano harvesters in Battambang province)

“Decades of collecting guano, right next to the bats, and I am healthy as ever. Maybe the risk is not that bad after all.” (A group of guano harvester in Kampot province)

PKLFPC’s Committed Participants

Reflecting similar sentiments as the other community under study, participants from Kampot province shared their apprehensions about the bat guano production process (Table 6). The task of harvesting was deemed moderately risky (average score: **5.5**), whereas the act of carrying the guano invoked a marginally higher level of concern (average score: **6.0**). Transporting the guano, however, was considered the least risky (average score: **1.6**), indicating that the degree of close contact with bat guano is a significant determinant in the perceived risk of contracting illnesses.

Table 6. Average level of concerns by activity rated by the committed participants

Task	Level of Concern (n=14) (1 to 10 – 1 is the least concern, 10 is the most concern)
Harvesting	5.5
Carrying	6.0
Transporting	1.6

“This is the only work I know, but it scares me a bit. What if I catch something from the bats, something we do not even know about yet? Just like COVID, it can come out of nowhere.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“Getting close to that bat guano really worries me. It seems like the harvesting and carrying tasks are the riskiest and transporting seems a lot safer.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

3.5 Negotiation and Intervention Kickoff

3.5.1 Negotiation and Advocacy Using Microeconomic Analysis

The execution of jointly developed RRI faced obstacles, particularly the reluctance of community members to incur the costs associated with procuring PPE and adopting new

hygiene protocols. To overcome this hurdle, the project team used various strategies. In the PRSFPC community, conversations shifted toward the distribution of profits throughout the overall value chain. As a result of these dialogues, the community leadership and committees, who benefit from a share of guano sales, consented to set aside a portion of these funds for the acquisition of PPE for their constituents, as depicted in Figure 4.

Meanwhile, in Kampot province, an alternate resolution took shape. The Provincial Department of Environment (PDOE) chose to support the implementation of the intervention, a decision influenced by the existing revenue-sharing model with the community. This model included a “protection fee” paid by the trader-cum-transporter (Figure 5).

Figure 4. A profit-sharing scheme in a guano harvesting community in Battambang province, PRSFPC

Figure 5. The bat guano harvesting and production value chain of PKLFPC in Kampot province

These alternative approaches, tailored to each community’s context, facilitated the negotiation process and ensured the implementation of RRI. The differences between these two communities are described in greater detail in the Participatory Assessment Report.

3.5.2 Overview of the Risk Reduction Interventions and Kickoff

Reflecting on identified risks, community members collaborated to create two primary interventions. Each intervention includes a set of “Good Practices” (GPs) aimed at reducing the risk of exposure to hazards such as bat droppings and dust.

In Kampot province, the commitment was unanimous among all 14 participants from the harvesting, carrying, and trader-transporter groups to adopt every GP outlined in the final menu (Table 7). Conversely, the PRSFPC community encountered some difficulties in this regard.

Table 7. Summary of listed interventions and committed participants in Kampot province

Group of Implementations	Intervention Items	Listed Interventions (which were self-reported by the community)					
		Intervention 1: Suboptimal use of PPE			Intervention 2: Hygiene practices		
		GP 1 (Fabric mask)	GP 2 (Fabric gloves)	GP 3 (Fisherman hat)	GP 4 (Washing hands)	GP 5 (Washing dedicated cloth)	GP 6 (Handwashing station)
Guano harvesters – Group 1		05 implemented GP1 – GP 6					
		03 implemented GP 1, GP 2			GP 4 – GP 6		
Guano sack (loading) carrier – Group 2		02 implemented GP 1 – GP6					
Trader-cum-transporter – Group 3		01 implemented GP 1 – GP6					
		01 implemented GP 1 – GP6					

Out of the permanent workforce, 26 guano workers stepped forward to volunteer, whereas the 27 temporary workers recruited for the high season abstained from participation. Notably, the community collectively devised an extra GP—the use of goggles—which was not part of the interventions in Kampot (Table 8). Nonetheless, each of the 26 PRSFPC participants pledged to adhere to all seven of the established GPs.

Table 8. Summary of listed interventions and committed participants in Battambang province

Intervention Items	Listed Interventions (which were self-reported by the community)						
	Intervention 1: Suboptimal use of PPE				Intervention 2: Hygiene practices		
	GP 1 (Fabric mask)	GP 2 (Fabric gloves)	GP 3 (Fisherman hat)	GP 4 (Goggles)	GP 5 (Washing hands)	GP 6 (Washing dedicated cloth)	GP 7 (Handwashing station)
Group of Implementations							
Guano harvesters – Group 1		05 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
		05 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
Guano sack (loading) carrier – Group 2		03 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
		03 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
Guano sack dropper – Group 3		01 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
		03 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
Guano sack sewer – Group 4		02 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					
Transporter – Group 5		04 implemented GP 1 – GP 7					

The analogous conditions in which the communities operate resulted in comparable designs for the interventions. Nevertheless, the diminished rate of involvement in PRSFPC underscores the difficulty in mobilizing temporary workers. Further studies are essential to decipher the factors contributing to this reduced engagement and to formulate approaches that could integrate temporary workers into subsequent interventions. Moreover, a thorough evaluation of the efficacy of these practices is vital to determine their success in mitigating health risks for the communities, which will be elaborated on in the subsequent section.

3.6 Specific Outcomes of Intervention Implementation

The preliminary evaluation conducted before initiating interventions in guano harvesting communities corroborated previous survey results. It was found that while all guano harvesters wore some form of head protection, the use of other PPE was at best inconsistent (Table 9). Specifically, eye protection and foot coverings were generally either absent or inadequately utilized.

Table 9. Summary of current PPE uses by the two target communities

Description	PRSFPC		PKLFPC	
	Current Practice	Kinds of Use	Current Practice	Kinds of Use
Head covering	Always	Krama	Sometimes	Krama
Eye shield	Never	One person (uses glasses to correct vision)	Never	
Nose/mouth: mask	Sometimes	Hat or T-shirt with attached scarf	Never	
Hand: gloves	Sometimes	Cloth, washable, gloves one-time use only	Never	
Upper body: garment	Always	Common clothes, dedicated clothes for cave work, sometimes short-sleeve blouse	Sometimes	Common clothes, dedicated clothes for bat caves
Lower body: garment	Always	Common clothes, dedicated clothes for bat caves, sometimes shorts	Sometimes	Common clothes, dedicated clothes for bat caves, sometimes shorts
Feet: boots	Never	Common shoes (flip flops), then took off when in the cave	Never	Common shoes (flip flops), took off before entering the caves

Based on the assessment, all committed community members agreed to participate in some use of PPE when working with bats or guano. They agreed primarily for health reasons:

“It helps me stay healthy and avoid getting sick.” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

“It keeps me healthy.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

3.6.1 Intervention I: Use of PPE

PRSFPC’s Committed Participants

The PRSFPC community operates on a unique guano collection timetable, as outlined in the Participatory Assessment Report. They engage in guano harvesting every 45 days, with the entire operation spanning six to seven days. Here is an overview of their routine:

- **Harvesting:** Conducted twice weekly, specifically in the evenings from 7 pm to 10 pm, over the course of two weeks (four days total: two days/week over a two-week period).
- **Processing:** Two days are allocated for bag replacement, sealing, guano transportation, and storage management.
- **Delivery:** The process culminates on the final day with the distribution of harvested guano to purchasers.

This cadence constrains the application of risk mitigation measures to a fortnightly period, effectively providing approximately seven days for the actual implementation of interventions.

During the midpoint evaluation, a notable observation was that all engaged participants consistently utilized the designated PPE. The most commonly adopted protective items included glasses, masks, gloves, long socks, and additional layers of clothing (Table 10). To further validate these observations, local OHDRaM WG trained representatives engaged in consultative dialogues and reviewed reminder sheets.

Table 10. Consolidated results from observations and consultative dialogues with participants from PRSFPC during the intervention period.

No.	Group of Implementations	First Week	Second Week	Third Week	Comments
		Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items	
1	Guano harvesters – Group 1	100% use of proposed PPE items (<i>surgical mask, fabric gloves, fisherman hat, and goggles</i>)	100% use of proposed PPE items, except the goggles		Darkness in cave, breathing creates fog in goggles, easy to fall off
2	Guano sack (loading) carrier – Group 2	100% use of proposed PPE items	100% use of proposed PPE items, except goggles		Task nature requires fast moving, goggles easily fall off
3	Guano sack dropper – Group 3	100% use of proposed PPE items	100% use of proposed PPE items		
4	Guano sack sewer – Group 4	100% use of proposed PPE items	100% use of proposed PPE items		
5	Transporter – Group 5	100% use of proposed PPE items	100% use of proposed PPE items		

“While masks are generally comfortable to use, they can cause our goggles to fog up, further restricting vision and hindering movement during guano harvesting.” (A group of guano harvesters in Battambang province)

“The provided goggles seem well-suited for tasks performed outside the cave, such as dropping or sewing guano bags. However, they are not ideal for the cave environment. They tend to fall off easily, and using dirty gloves to hold them in place is not only inconvenient but poses potential hygiene risks.” (A group of guano harvesters in Battambang province).

*“The goggles and other PPE work great for us when we are outside the cave during the day. We appreciate the focus on safety and feel comfortable using everything that's been proposed.”
(A group of guano droppers in Battambang province)*

PKLFPC’s Committed Participants

The PDOE’s backing of the PKLFPC community’s risk mitigation interventions was a welcome gesture, albeit with limited scope. Regrettably, their funding only extended to the acquisition of hats, leaving community members to bear the cost of remaining PPE. Initial assessments combining midpoint consultative dialogues, direct observations, and analysis of completed reminder sheets indicated a predominant use of only the provided fisherman hats. The absence of masks and gloves was noticeable.

The delay in comprehensive PPE usage was attributed to:

- **Limited Access:** Participants reported constraints in purchasing PPE due to time restrictions and the unavailability of certain items in local markets.
- **Adjustment Period:** Several individuals faced difficulties in adapting to the use of PPE.

*“Due to current workload constraints, I haven’t been able to purchase the requested PPE yet.”
(A female guano harvester in Kampot province)*

“Wearing gloves presents some challenges for my work tasks. Additionally, I’m still adjusting to using a mask while working.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

Despite these challenges, a shift toward better compliance was noted. By the second week, half of engaged participants had begun to utilize the full set of PPE. This improvement was bolstered by ongoing encouragement and assistance during the midpoint dialogues. By the third week, it was observed that all participants had adopted the complete array of PPE as per the intervention guidelines (Table 11).

In contrast to PRSFPC, the PKLFPC community engages in daily guano harvesting. Consequently, they had more time to test and modify PPE use throughout the 21-day intervention period. They consistently grappled with the suboptimal application of the proposed PPE.

Table 11. Consolidated results from observations and consultative dialogues with PKLFPC participants during the intervention period.

No.	Group of Implementations	First Week	Second Week	Third Week
		Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items
I	Guano harvesters – Group I	50% use of proposed PPE items (<i>surgical mask, fabric gloves, fisherman hat</i>).	50% use of proposed PPE items (<i>surgical mask, fabric gloves, fisherman hat</i>).	100% use of all proposed PPE items

No.	Group of Implementations	First Week	Second Week	Third Week
		Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items	Worn PPE items
		50% wore only the fisherman hat	50% wore only the fisherman hat	
2	Guano sack (loading) carrier – Group 2	No use of all proposed PPE items (wore only fisherman hat)	No use of all proposed PPE items (wore only fisherman hat)	100% use of all proposed PPE items
3	Trader-cum-transporter – Group 3	100% use of all proposed PPE items	100% use of proposed PPE items	100% use of all proposed PPE items

3.6.2 Intervention 2: Hygiene Practices

PRSFPC

Washing Station and Handwashing

Demonstrating strong leadership and commitment, the community committee provided two dedicated handwashing stations. One is located near the cave entrance for those harvesting guano, sewing, and dropping guano bags. The other is situated downhill for those unloading, loading, and transporting guano. Each station is equipped with three large plastic containers for water, liquid soap, and two towels.

During midpoint dialogues, all participants confirmed their consistent practice of handwashing:

- After any contact with guano or related materials throughout the harvesting operation; and
- Before eating or drinking food and water.

“We learned that dirty hands can spread illness, especially from bat guano. So, whenever we take a break from the cave, we always wash our hands before opening our water bottles.” (A female and male guano harvester in Kampot province)

“I noticed feeling unwell when I didn’t wash my hands properly. Now, I wash with the provided liquid soap every hour during my snack break.” (A female and male guano harvester in Battambang province)

“My group decided to leave food and water outside the cave. Before enjoying snacks, we wash our hands. We help each other by taking turns pouring water and cleaning hands.” (A female and male guano harvester in Battambang province)

Daily Washing of Dedicated Clothes

We observed noteworthy practices regarding clothing hygiene among the bat guano harvesters. This group, consisting of 10 members, demonstrated exemplary cleanliness by changing out of their soiled garments while on break. They came prepared with additional sets of clothing to

maintain hygiene throughout the prolonged harvesting sessions. After leaving the cave, they carefully took off their work-specific attire, packed each item separately, and took them home to launder the next day. This routine guaranteed that the clothes were thoroughly dried before their next use, as the late hours from harvesting did not permit overnight washing.

“Changing clothes regularly has become a routine for us. We learned that it helps protect us from getting sick, and honestly, we just started feeling icky in dirty clothes.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“After each break, we swap into a fresh set. We also pack our used clothes in plastic bags to keep them separate. Washing everything before reuse is a must.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“The only challenge is that we often get back home late and exhausted. So, while we’d love to wash them right away, we end up keeping them outside overnight and washing them first thing in the morning.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

The study observed a distinct approach among the 16 participants engaged in activities other than direct harvesting. According to observations and data from their reminder sheets, it was consistently observed that they washed their soiled clothing on the day of work, usually in the afternoon following their morning guano-related duties. A positive note from the midpoint check-in was that all participants, irrespective of their specific roles, used detergent in cleaning their contaminated attire. This uniform adherence underscores dedication to maintaining hygiene standards among all study participants.

PKLFPC

Washing Station and Handwashing

While harvesters have not yet adopted the practice of washing hands with soap before drinking water inside the cave, a positive change was observed. They are now removing their gloves before opening their water bottles to drink. Additionally, they have significantly reduced the practice of bringing food into the cave, opting for water only.

“Thorough handwashing inside the cave presents logistical difficulties. First, it would likely require two people to assist each other, making it cumbersome. Second, carrying the additional water bottles uphill for proper handwashing would be quite burdensome.” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

Upon leaving the cave, a more regular practice of handwashing was noted. The community committee, in partnership with the PDOE, set up a handwashing facility equipped with sealed concrete sinks, a soap dispenser, and an accessible water source. This installation significantly improved the practice of handwashing prior to consuming food or beverages.

“Here outside the cave, the handwashing station with running water from the concrete basin and readily available detergent makes it convenient to clean our hands.” (Two female guano harvesters in Kampot province)

“Having access to detergent and water allows us to practice proper handwashing, which is crucial for preventing the spread of germs and maintaining good hygiene.” (Two male guano harvesters in Kampot province)

Although there were some initial hurdles, the outcome was ultimately successful. Through discussions and monitoring, it was verified that all 14 dedicated participants consistently washed their hands with soap each time they exited the cave for meals.

Daily Washing of Dedicated Clothes

The study found that all participants who had committed to the program diligently adhered to a routine of laundering their work-specific clothing daily after arriving home. This was corroborated by sporadic checks conducted by the monitoring team, which affirmed that each participant engaged in this practice. The team’s reports indicated that the participants arrived home and proceeded to wash their clothes in the afternoon, consistently using detergent for the task.

During midpoint check-in dialogues, participants explained their reasons for daily washing:

- **Hygiene and Odor Control:** Dirty clothes become smelly after a day’s work, prompting washing.
- **Germ Awareness:** Participants learned the importance of removing potential germs from their clothes by washing them daily.

The limited number of extra clothes (only two sets per person) also made daily washing necessary to ensure a clean set for the next day’s harvesting.

“Who wants to work in stinky clothes all day? Washing them every night after harvest makes a big difference. Plus, now I know those dirty clothes can carry germs, so washing them daily is a must!” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

“Two sets of clothes just will not cut it! Harvesting is messy work, and we need clean clothes every day. Luckily, the monitoring team saw me washing mine this afternoon – good timing!” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

“Since learning about germs, I am more careful about everything. Washing my work clothes every day is a small step, but it helps keep me healthy. Besides, who wants to sleep in clothes that smell like bat guano?” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

3.7 Endpoint Assessment

3.7.1 Intervention I: Use of PPE

PRSFPC

The implementation of this intervention yielded mixed results. By the end of the three-week period, all participating groups had improved their PPE practices, although many still fell short of optimal practice. The most frequently used and correctly worn PPE items were masks (26/26), hats (head coverings), upper body garments (an extra layer of dedicated clothing), and gloves. However, guano harvesters and carriers initially used eye shields but completely stopped using them during the second week of implementation (as shown in Table 11). The primary challenge they encountered while using proper PPE and adhering to regular practices was discomfort when working with goggles in the cave.

“We encountered some difficulties using goggles while working inside the cave at night. Due to the limited visibility, wearing goggles significantly hinders our ability to navigate safely.” (A group of female guano harvesters in Battambang province)

“Working with a mask, gloves, and goggles is a bit of an adjustment. It is tough to breathe at first, but I am getting there.” (A group of male guano harvesters in Battambang province)

Table 12. Summary of the committed participants who successfully implemented the suboptimal use of PPE

List of PPE to Use During the Implementation (Total committed participants = 26)	No. of Agreed to Pilot the Interventions	No. of Succeed	No. of Intent to Continue
Fabric masks	26	26	26
Fabric gloves	26	26	26
Fisherman hats	26	26	26
Goggles	26	10	10

While achieving the target level of PPE use presented challenges for some participants, all expressed a strong desire to maintain their current practices and further refine them to align fully with the established interventions. Their commitment to continued PPE use was driven by health and safety concerns.

“Keep my family healthy and safe from illness.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“This serves as a constant nudge to prioritize my own safety.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“Wearing PPE is crucial for my job to prevent exposure to hazards.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

Throughout implementation, all 26 participants discussed PPE practices with their family members, emphasizing the importance of staying safe and protecting their families. However, none of them engaged in conversations with their neighbors about their practices. Participants were preoccupied with their farming work, and they hesitated to discuss PPE with neighbors until they felt confident in their own adherence.

“I discussed safety measures with my family to protect against infectious diseases, but I have not yet shared this information with others. I want to ensure that I can practice it effectively on my own before spreading the word.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“I spoke with my family, but I have not had the chance to meet my neighbor yet.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

“I have had conversations with my daughter and grandchildren, but I have not mustered the courage to approach my neighbor about it yet.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

PKLFPC

Similar to PRSFPC, intervention implementation among dedicated PKLFPC participants yielded mixed results. By the conclusion of the three-week period, all participating guano groups had improved their PPE practices, although they encountered initial challenges. The most frequently used and correctly worn PPE items included hats (head coverings), masks, gloves, and additional clothing (Table 13).

Table 13. Summary of the committed participants who successfully implemented the use of PPE

List of PPE to Use During the Implementation (Total committed participants = 26)	No. of Agreed to Pilot the Interventions	No. of Succeed	No. of Intent to Continue
Fabric masks	14	14	14
Fabric gloves	14	14	14
Fisherman hats	14	14	14

The primary challenge they encountered while using proper PPE and adhering to regular practices was discomfort when working with gloves.

“These gloves are a pain to work with when harvesting guano. Taking them off just to open a water bottle is a real hassle, but the dust is brutal otherwise.” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

“Maintaining proper hand hygiene while harvesting guano presents a challenge. The cumbersome gloves make it difficult to remove and replace them frequently, especially for simple tasks like accessing a water bottle.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

Participants in the intervention faced difficulties finding proper PPE in the village and local market, particularly masks and good-quality gloves. Additionally, competing demands prevented them from seeking PPE elsewhere.

Despite these challenges, all participants committed to continuing their PPE practices and striving to improve in areas where they fell short. Their motivation for persisting with PPE usage included safety concerns and a desire to protect themselves and others.

“By using PPE, I am protecting myself and those around me.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

“It keeps me focused on staying safe.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

“Using PPE is an essential part of my safety routine.” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

The 14 participants discussed the agreed-upon PPE practices with their families, emphasizing how these measures would keep them safe and protect their loved ones. However, due to their personal businesses, they have not yet had the opportunity to talk to their neighbors about the program. They felt it would be more appropriate to discuss it after becoming more comfortable and proficient with using PPE themselves.

“I talked to my family about using PPE to stay safe from germs. I want to get comfortable with it myself before sharing it with others.” (A male guano harvester in Kampot province)

“I chatted with my family, but I have not had a chance to meet my neighbor yet.” (A female guano harvester in Kampot province)

3.7.2 Intervention 2: Hygiene Practices

PRSFPC

Washing Station and Handwashing

The handwashing intervention yielded positive results. This community, which initially lacked proper handwashing facilities, like a good water dispenser, showed significant improvement by the end of the three-week period. Notably, all participants adopted the habit of using water and liquid soap for handwashing.

The handwashing procedure itself underwent a positive change. Previously, participants used the same bowls without rinsing for handwashing. This practice was replaced with a double-washing method: first, hands were washed with liquid soap and water in plastic bowls, followed by a rinse with clean water poured by a peer.

However, the use of only two towels for hand drying remained a suboptimal practice for many participants.

“If I dried my hands with the same towels, which were used by many people (it was already wet), my hands may get dirty again. I wash my hands and shake them a bit, then it is ok.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

The 26 participants are actively integrating handwashing into their routines.

“Since learning about proper handwashing, I’ve made it a habit to wash my hands frequently. I also bring my own towel for better hygiene.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

Their primary motivation for adopting the practice stemmed from a desire to improve their health and prevent the spread of infectious diseases.

“Practice good hygiene to keep your family healthy and safe from germs.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

“Regular handwashing is a powerful tool to keep our families safe from illness.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

While participants discussed handwashing with their families, they have not yet had the opportunity to share these practices with their neighbors. Many felt they needed more time to solidify their own routines and gain confidence before promoting them to others. However, they expressed interest in future neighbor discussions once they felt fully comfortable.

“I’m still learning the best way to wash my hands. Once I’ve got it down, I’d love to show my neighbor.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

“I’ve had a conversation with my family. I’m also open to discussing with my neighbors if they seek information, although it seems they often lack the time for such exchanges.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

Daily Washing of Dedicated Clothes

The intervention to improve contaminated clothing hygiene proved successful. By the end of the three weeks, all 26 participants significantly improved their washing practices. Despite returning home late and being unable to wash immediately, everyone adopted a new routine: soaking clothes in a detergent solution overnight for a thorough clean, followed by washing them first thing in the morning.

This new practice led to a sense of satisfaction and peace of mind among the participants. They expressed happiness at seeing their work clothes clean and “hygienic.”

“I cannot see if there is any virus and bat dropping on clothes because I sweep the guano and move inside the bat caves. So, washing my clothes and working materials is a necessary work and this is what I am wishing for.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

The 26 participants enthusiastically embraced the new hygiene practices and expressed strong commitment to sharing them with their families. This includes spouses, children, parents, and even grandchildren, creating a ripple effect of improved hygiene habits across generations.

“I will tell my daughters and grandchildren to keep good hygiene by washing clothes every morning with detergent. We have to live in good hygiene because we are working close to the bat/guano.” (A male guano harvester in Battambang province)

“Working near bats and handling guano requires caution due to potential zoonotic viruses. Good hygiene is essential.” (A female guano harvester in Battambang province)

PKLFPC

Washing Station and Handwashing

The handwashing intervention yielded significant results, particularly for those households lacking proper facilities. By the end of the three weeks, the community with limited access to supplied water and detergent demonstrated marked improvement. Notably, all participants embraced the use of detergent for handwashing. Additionally, a concrete basin supplied with pumped groundwater has been installed to provide a dedicated handwashing station.

The handwashing procedure itself underwent a positive transformation also. Previously, participants resorted to drying their hands on clothing, which posed a hygiene risk. This practice was significantly improved as everyone adopted the habit of bringing a clean cloth specifically for individual hand drying.

“Washing hands is pointless if dried with a dirty shirt! We’re all bringing clean towels now.” (A group of male guano harvesters in Kampot province)

Driven by a desire to improve their health and prevent the spread of illness, all 14 participants have successfully ingrained handwashing into their daily routines.

“Taking a simple step like washing your hands frequently can significantly reduce your risk of catching colds, flu, and other illnesses.” (A group of guano trader-cum-transporter in Kampot province)

Having discussed handwashing with their families, participants are now eager to share these practices with their neighbors. Many recognize the value of promoting good hygiene within the community.

“Handwashing is a habit I discussed with my family, and I’m eager to share its importance with neighbors too! Good hygiene benefits everyone, and it’s something we can all work on together. The reminders on TV during COVID-19 really highlighted its importance for me.” (A group of female guano harvesters in Kampot province)

Daily Washing of Dedicated Clothes

The intervention to improve contaminated clothing hygiene yielded impressive results. After just three weeks, all 14 participants demonstrated a strong commitment to proper washing practices. This newfound diligence led to a sense of satisfaction and peace of mind among the participants. They expressed joy at seeing their work clothes clean and meeting their hygiene standards.

“We actually washed our clothes daily, but there was room for improvement. Previously, we’d wash our work clothes with other laundry, leaving them last. This meant less detergent and potentially not enough cleaning power for the dirtier items. Now, we wash our work clothes separately with a good amount of detergent, ensuring they’re properly cleaned and free of any strong odors.” (A group of guano harvesters in Kampot province)

Inspired by the intervention, all 14 dedicated individuals eagerly adopted the new hygiene practices. Their enthusiasm extends beyond themselves, as they have committed to sharing these valuable habits with their families—spouses, children, and parents, but not neighbors yet.

“We discussed the new way of washing our work clothes (especially those contaminated with bat guano) with our families. This was particularly important because sometimes our children would help with laundry, and we wanted them to understand the proper way to handle these specific items.” (A group of male guano harvesters in Kampot province)

“We hesitated to share our new clothes washing routine with the neighbors because their laundry habits might be different. We would not want them to feel pressured to change their ways or feel uncomfortable if they wash their clothes differently.” (A group of female guano harvesters in Kampot province)

4.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This interim report, focused on community-level RRI at bat guano harvest sites in Kampot and Battambang provinces, provides valuable insights into the behaviors and practices of guano harvesters, and the effectiveness of the implemented interventions. The participatory approach adopted by the project has been instrumental in identifying and addressing the specific needs and challenges faced by the guano harvesting communities while ensuring local voices are heard. By engaging community members in the design and testing of interventions, the project has ensured that the strategies are contextually relevant and have a higher likelihood of being sustained.

The interventions focused on two main areas: the use of PPE and hygiene practices. The commitment shown by the community members, particularly in adopting the use of PPE and establishing and using handwashing stations, is commendable. The project's efforts to negotiate and advocate through profit/loss analysis have also been successful in securing community buy-in and support for the interventions.

The implementation of PPE and hygiene practices in the two communities presents a case study in the adoption of health and safety measures in high-risk environments. The initial commitment of the PRSFPC community to adopt all proposed PPE items is commendable. However, the practical challenges faced, such as the fogging of goggles inside the cave, highlight the need for PPE that is not only protective but also adaptable to the working conditions of guano harvesters working in caves. The effective use of PPE outside the cave by PRSFPC participants indicates a positive behavioral change toward personal safety.

In the PKLFPC community, the gradual adoption of the full set of PPE, with the initial use of hats evolving to include masks and gloves, demonstrates the impact of sustained guidance and support. This incremental approach may serve as a model for other communities where immediate comprehensive adoption of PPE is challenging.

The establishment of handwashing stations by both communities and the consistent practice of handwashing signify a proactive stance toward hygiene. This is particularly noteworthy as hand hygiene is a critical component in preventing the spread of zoonotic diseases. Given the ample exposure of harvesters' hands to any pathogens present in bat guano, hand hygiene must be an important plank of any risk reduction strategy for guano harvesters.

Community engagement, as evidenced by the varying levels of intervention implementation due to the guano harvesting schedules, underscores the importance of tailoring interventions to fit the unique rhythms of community activities. The continuous practice of interventions in the PKLFPC community, facilitated by their daily harvesting schedule, may enhance long-term adherence.

The positive changes observed during the intervention period, such as the consistent use of PPE and adherence to handwashing protocols, are promising indicators of the project's impact. The significant improvement in the community's understanding of zoonotic diseases and the importance of biosafety measures, as evidenced by the pre- and post-test results, further underscores the value of STOP Spillover's work.

However, challenges remain. The limited participation of temporary workers in PRSFPC and the initial reluctance of PKLFPC members to fully adopt PPE due to financial constraints highlight the need for continued support and innovative solutions to ensure widespread adoption of risk reduction practices.

As the project moves forward, it is crucial to maintain the momentum gained and to continue refining interventions based on feedback and experiences of community members. The endpoint consultative assessment will be a critical step in evaluating the long-term effectiveness of these interventions and in identifying areas for further improvement.

In conclusion, STOP Spillover's interim report highlights the progress made in reducing the risk of zoonotic disease transmission in bat guano harvesting communities. The collaborative and participatory nature of the project has been key to its success thus far. Continued engagement, monitoring, and adaptation of the interventions will be essential to ensure that the communities are equipped to sustain these risk reduction practices and protect themselves from the threat of zoonotic diseases. The project serves as a model for similar initiatives worldwide, demonstrating the importance of community involvement and tailored interventions in addressing global health challenges.

5.0 RECOMMENDATIONS AND NEXT STEPS

5.1 Recommendations

1. **PPE Improvement:** Research and introduce anti-fogging technology or alternative PPE that accommodates the unique conditions of cave environments to ensure full compliance and comfort for the harvesters.
2. **Incremental Adoption Strategy:** Continue to support communities with a phased approach to PPE adoption, providing education and resources to facilitate gradual integration of safety measures.
3. **Hygiene Promotion:** Maintain and expand the handwashing stations and continue to promote their use through regular community engagement activities.
4. **Flexible Intervention Schedule:** Adapt intervention schedules to align with the community's harvesting activities, ensuring that health and safety practices are seamlessly incorporated into their daily work.
5. **Community Involvement:** Foster a sense of ownership and responsibility within the community for the sustained practice of interventions, encouraging local leaders to champion these efforts.

By addressing these recommendations, the communities can enhance their resilience against health risks and set a precedent for other guano harvesting regions to follow.

5.2 Next Steps

As we move forward from the findings and successes of the current interventions, it is crucial to build on the momentum and scale our efforts. The following next steps are designed to enhance the impact and reach of our risk reduction strategies:

- **Scaling Up Good Practices:**
 - Expand the implementation of proven RRI within the existing communities and across other guano harvesting communities;
 - Develop a standardized set of best practices that can be adapted to different environmental and community contexts; and
 - Foster partnerships with local authorities and organizations to support the widespread adoption of these practices.

- Awareness Through Education:
 - Launch demonstration-based education campaigns that provide hands-on experiences and interactive learning opportunities;
 - Utilize multimedia tools (social behavior change and communication materials) and local languages to ensure the message resonates with diverse audiences; and
 - Measure the effectiveness of these campaigns through community feedback and adjust strategies accordingly.
- Cross-Province Learning:
 - Facilitate shared learning experiences and exchange visits between target provinces to foster a collaborative approach to risk reduction;
 - Document and disseminate lessons learned from each province to create a knowledge base that can inform future interventions; and
 - Encourage community leaders to participate in these exchanges to champion the cause within their communities.
- Networking and Workshops:
 - Organize national workshops that bring together stakeholders from various regions to share experiences and network;
 - Create platforms for discussion and collaboration that can lead to innovative solutions and stronger community engagement; and
 - Develop a national action plan that outlines the roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders in scaling up interventions.

By focusing on these next steps, we can ensure that the progress made is not only sustained but also amplified, leading to a safer and healthier future for all communities involved in bat guano harvesting.

6.0 ANNEXES

Annex 1: Timeline for Intervention Implementation in Kampot and Battambang Provinces

Activity	Feb				Mar				Apr				May				Jun				
	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	
Training material and tools development																					
Tele-training the OHDWG members in Kampot & Battambang																					
Awareness campaigns in Kampot & Battambang									[----- -----]												
PPE market survey: availability and prices																					
Initial Interviews and agreement on intervention																					
Initial intervention period (harvesting period)																					
Mid-point check-in																					
Final intervention period																					
Endpoint assessment																					
Data review and entry																					
Analysis																					
Reporting and sharing																					

Annex 2: Participant Record

OH-DReaM WG Members in Kampot Province

No.	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Chhim Meng	M	Technical Official – Community	PDOE
2	Sorng Chea	M	Official – FA	PDAFF
3	Toach Sopheary	F	Official - RRT	PHD
4	Chhay Sophea	M	Health Official	OD – Kampong Trach
5	Koeum SamAn	M	Official – District Vet	District Hall – Banteay Meas
6	Lin Chanthorn	F	Commune Council for Women & Children (CCWC)	Commune Hall
7	In Ratha	M	Health Official – Health Center	Touk Meas Lech – HC
8	Chey Puth	M	Village Chief	Chrok Khlai
9	Soung Chheun	M	Community Head	PKLFPC
10	Bun Chan	M	Technical Official - GDAHP	GDAHP
11	Chea Sokun	M	OH Secretariate	MAFF
12	Sao Sovan	M	Technical Official – Cambodia CDC	Cambodia CDC
13	Ren Theary	F	Technical Official – NAHPRI	NAHPRI
TOTAL				13

OH-DReaM WG Members in Battambang Province

No.	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Soung Piseth	M	Technical Official – Community Development	PDOE
2	Uy Vanna	M	Official – FA	PDAFF
3	Sin Sothy	F	Official - RRT	PHD
4	Khuy Sopheak	M	Health Official	OD – Battambang
5	Mao Chhoub	F	Official – District Vet	District Hall – Banan
6	Kean Mom	F	Commune Council for Women & Children (CCWC)	Commune Hall - Kanteou
7	Thagn Kimyirt	M	Health Official – Health Center	Kantoeu II – HC
8	Chao Chern	M	Village Chief	Chrok Khlai
9	Lun Bunlern	M	Community Head	PRSSFPC
10	Oam Phalline	F	Health Official – Health Center	Sampoeu – HC
11	Heng Sophea	M	Technical Official - GDAHP	GDAHP
12	Sar Sophireak	F	OH Secretariate	MAFF
13	Chheib Sunheng	M	Technical Official – Cambodia CDC	Cambodia CDC
14	Ren Theary	F	Technical Official – NAHPRI	NAHPRI
TOTAL				14

Community Members/participants in Kampot Province

No.	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Ouch Sreyrov	F	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
2	Soam Ly	M	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
3	Chhoub Noch	F	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
4	Yorng Pouy	M	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
5	Chhoub Phea	F	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
6	Sanh Rathana	F	Traders-cum-Transporters	PKLFPC
7	Hin Merl	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
8	Koun In	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
9	Cheak Ny	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
10	Khnor Hi	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
11	Seat Hing	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
12	Sorng Chorn	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
13	Chov Khvin	M	Carrier	PKLFPC
14	Orng Reth	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
15	Khnor Khav	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
16	Chem Pich	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
17	Khnor Saron	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
18	Khim Enn	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
19	Mith Lot	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
20	Sok Sophorn	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
21	Thy Teur	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
22	Khim Puth	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
23	Keam Vuthy	M	Carrier	PKLFPC
24	Chean Sreyneang	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
25	Chun Phal	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
26	Dy Vik	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
27	Chan Ra	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
28	Khnor Phanny	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
29	Phee Kina	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
30	Sorng Srey	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
31	Ork Earch	M	Carrier	PKLFPC
32	Min Sophal	F	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
33	Kong Run	M	Guano Harvester	PKLFPC
34	Sorn Chin	M	Carrier	PKLFPC
TOTAL				34

Community Members/participants in Battambang Province

No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
1	Mao Chamroeun	M	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
2	Vith Phan	M	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
3	Roeun Ry	M	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
4	Mao Reth	F	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
5	Sokha Sideth	M	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
6	Lath Malai	F	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
7	Sokha nak	F	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
8	Sokha Chaidy	F	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
9	Min Sochert	M	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
10	Rom Sopha	F	Guano Harvester	PRSSFPC
11	Ratt Rong	M	Carrier	PRSSFPC
12	Ratt Rouy	F	Carrier	PRSSFPC
13	Rong Nich	M	Carrier	PRSSFPC
14	Orng Rith	M	Carrier	PRSSFPC
15	Khav Vika	M	Carrier	PRSSFPC
16	Cheng Vatha	M	Carrier	PRSSFPC
17	Souy Mab	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
18	Lun BunLern	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
19	Sin Vibol	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
20	Tim Chan	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
21	Chit Veasna	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
22	Min Srey	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
23	Dy Na	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
24	Tha Chenda	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
25	Chan Chorvy	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
26	Bin Sitha	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
27	Hok Neang	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
28	Se Phalla	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
29	Khy Thearo	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC

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No	Name	Sex	Position	Institution
30	Khy Theary	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
31	Kuy Nha	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
32	Phy Sopheab	F	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
33	Keo Kan	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
34	Dy Sina	M	Seamstress	PRSSFPC
35	Meach Kong	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
36	Vorn Rath	F	Dropper	PRSSFPC
37	Rom Reth	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
38	Chean Chhea	F	Dropper	PRSSFPC
39	Ching Kear	F	Dropper	PRSSFPC
40	Sao Mean	F	Dropper	PRSSFPC
41	Sok Sameoun	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
42	Keo Kong	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
43	Nong Hak	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
44	Seng Thy	M	Dropper	PRSSFPC
45	Nath Nann	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
46	Houy Chit	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
47	Khan Hort	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
48	Sang Kimsert	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
49	Hak Nit	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
50	Chea Sarun	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
51	Leng Vanny	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
52	Kun Bophara	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
53	Leng Sat	M	Transporter	PRSSFPC
TOTAL				53

Annex 3: Consent Forms

Consent Information Sheet for Community Participants

Introduction

We read the responses from the first part of our team’s study at bat guano harvesting communities and have identified at least six different practices to increase safety and reduce the risk of diseases spreading from bats to humans. The use of risk reduction interventions (RRIs) will help caved bat guano harvesters to experience the solutions for using practices to reduce these risks. The overall goal of this study is to identify good practices of the two identified interventions that reduce this risk and that work for harvesting communities in the long term.

Protocol Title: Community-level risk reduction interventions

Local Investigator’s name: Srey Chanthy

Principal Investigator’s name: Hellen Amuguni (USA)

Organization: Tetra Tech-Branch ARD, and Tufts University (USA)

You are invited to take part in this study being conducted by Dr. Hellen Amuguni, researchers from Tufts University and Mr. Srey Chanthy, the Cambodia STOP Spillover Country Team Lead. We are hoping that your participation in this study will help solve the main risks and that your expectations of what good practices look like can help you and other people in your community reduce the risk of diseases spreading from bats to humans. The whole RRI process will take about one month and will involve 3 visits from the study team, and during your participation, you will try some biosafety and hygiene practices. Throughout the process, we will check in with you to see how the trials of these improved practices are going. This activity is part of a larger project, called “STOP Spillover”, funded by USAID. This project aims to reduce the risk of diseases spreading from animals to humans. It also aims to share information on the risks of close contact with animals. We would like to invite you to read (or have read to you) this consent document to understand what participating in this study would mean for you.

If you decide to be in this study, you will be invited to participate in an initial household education and interview by the study team as the first visit and to start intervention of not more than two selected interventions. The second household visit will be conducted in the following one or two weeks by the study team to check and consult your implementation progress, and the final visit and consultative dialogues will be conducted in the next third or fourth week to assess the results and its effectiveness. If you decide to participate in this study, you agree to discuss plans together with us in order to start the intervention.

Why am I invited to participate in the study?

You are being invited to take part in the RRI because you have participated in the earlier surveys on risk reduction related to bat guano production in your communities. You have been invited to participate in the RRI pilot because of your valuable roles, expertise, or both.

Privacy and Confidentiality

By signing this consent form, you agree to participate in the trials and agree to allow the project to take photos, videos and audio records. You also agree to provide your personal contact information such as name and location. We may use information collected from you to produce film documentaries and written success stories. We might also use video and audio recordings from the RRI for these as well.

There is a risk of loss of confidentiality, meaning your private information could be seen by someone outside of the research team. In order to minimize this risk, your answers will be labeled with a code and kept separate from your personal information. We will keep all information from this study on a special computer that only study staff will be able to get access to. We will not share your identifying information with anyone. In videos and photos produced from our study, we will be sure to blur your faces to protect your identity.

Your mobile telephone number will be temporarily kept while the study is being done. We may keep your contact information and invite you to participate in any future related studies or we can contact you for any questions we have for a maximum of 3 years. This information will be destroyed after the RRI research has been completed, within 3 years of RRI completion. Only study staff will have access to this information.

Future Use of Information

Other researchers might want to use the information collected from the interventions and if they get approval, we will share information with them without any of your identifying information (no name, phone number, etc.) We will not share your identifying information with anyone and any videos/photos we produce from this study will have your faces blurred to protect your identity.

Right to Participate

If you decide not to participate in the study there is no penalty for you, as participating is voluntary. You can stop participating at any time with no penalty to you and skip any questions you do not want to answer.

Benefits and Payment

There are no direct benefits to you from taking part in the study. We cannot promise any benefits to others from your taking part in this study. However, there would be possible benefits to the people living in your communities and country if it helps to reduce the risk of pandemic virus spreading from bats to humans. It is possible that your participation may indirectly improve the biosafety and hygiene practices among your household members and community members to reduce the risk of diseases spreading from bats to humans. You will not be paid for participating in this study, but you may benefit from possible increased protection from PPE (personal protective equipment) and good hygiene practices if you properly apply it.

This study has been reviewed by the Cambodia National Ethics Committee for Health Research (NECHR). If you have any questions, concerns, complaints or think the research study has hurt you, you may talk to me now or you may contact Mr. Srey Chanthly, who is the Cambodia Country Team Lead.

He is available at chanthy.srey@tetrattech.com and by phone at +855 12 943 609. You may also contact Dr. Hellen Amuguni, Principal Investigator, at janetrix.amuguni@tufts.edu

If you have questions about your rights as a research study subject, you may contact the Cambodia IRB at nouthsarida@gmail.com and by phone at +855 12 528 789.

The study team will keep contact information for possible future participation.

Thank you for your participation.

Signature of Agreement by Participant

Written Name of the Community's Rep.

Date of signing:/...../.....

Signature of Project Activity Lead

Written name of Project Activity Lead

Annex 4: Initial Consultative Dialogue

INTERVIEW GUIDE—INITIAL CONSULTATIVE DIALOGUE

[CAVED BAT GUANO HARVESTING COMMUNITY (CBGHC)]

Respondent's ID:

CBGHC code 001 (Note— Try to discuss and mingle with the group of community following the flow of questions in this form. After the problems have been diagnosed, the primary actor for the improved practice can be identified for the intervention trials)

Name of the Consultative Dialogue Conductors:

Date of visit...../...../..... (dd/mm/yyyy), Time

PART I—ASSESSMENT (Note: this follows the confirmation of consent and the explanation about the study)

Thank you again for agreeing to participate with us in looking for ways to help everyone here live healthy lives while providing a home for bats. Before we talk about the specific practices you might try, I would like to learn more about your current practices.

Let's start with personal protection for all people in your family who are in direct contact with guano. This means for harvesting the guano, packing the guano for sale, or applying the guano on your crops. It also includes the times when people guard the cave.

1. Who typically performs these tasks?

- Harvesting the guano: _____
- Packing/sewing guano for sale: _____
- Carrying the guano: _____
- Guarding the cave and caved bats: _____
- Transporting the guano: _____
- Dropping down the guano: _____

NOTE: If the main community members involved in these activities is different from the person being interviewed, please invite those active in these activities to join the discussion.

2. During these activities of harvesting, packing/sewing, carrying, guarding, transporting, and dropping or others in the household are in direct contact with the bats' urine and feces.

- When performing the activity do you have concerns for your own safety? ___Y / N
- If yes, on a scale of 1-10 with 10 being high concern and 1 being little concern where would you place your level of concern? _____
- What are your concerns?
- If not, what makes you feel safe doing the work?
- For interviewer for each person involved in the activity:

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Task	Concern Y / N	Level	Why?
Harvesting			
Packing/sewing			
Carrying the guano			
Guarding			
Transporting the guano			
Dropping the guano			

3. Let's talk about your use of protective covering when you perform these tasks. A full set of covering goes from head to toe. For each task I am going to ask you about any covering your current use. If you use something, I am interested in what and if you use it always or only at certain times and why. (Note different people may answer these questions by task.)

Task	Head	Eyes	Nose/mouth	Hands	Body	Feet
Collecting guano						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						
Packing/sewing						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						
Carrying the guano						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						
Transporting the guano						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						

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Task	Head	Eyes	Nose/mouth	Hands	Body	Feet
Guarding						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						
Dropping the guano						
Cover Y / N						
What						
When						

4. After you finish your task of guano harvesting or packing and you remove any protective wear, what do you do? Where do you take it off and where do you keep it? (Ask about each piece of protective wear that they use.)

- (Person I) _____

- (Person I) _____

- (Person I) _____

5. Do you wash or disinfect the protective wear after use? __Y / N

If yes, please describe what you do to clean it: _(If people have different , note them)_____

- (Person I) _____

- (Person I) _____

- (Person I) _____

6. Now I would like to know about cleaning yourself after contact with the guano or bats.

- What do you do?
- When you finish your work with guano or with the bat roosts, do you wash your hands? __Y / N
- If yes, where do you wash your hands?
- Is the handwashing facility close by? Do you need to enter the house to wash your hands?
- How do you wash your hands? (If they don't mention soap ask: Do you use soap? Is it always available to you?)
 - (Person I) _____

- (Person I) _____

7. Now I would like to ask you about the storage of the guano that you are harvesting for sale.

- What type of bag do you store the guano in? _____
- Where do you store guano? _____

PART 2–PRIORITIZING HOUSEHOLD PRACTICES: TAKE A BREAK TO REVIEW ANSWERS AND THE COMMUNITY SITUATION. USE TABLE BELOW TO SUMMARIZE YOUR ANSWERS AND PRIORITIZE THE AREAS MOST IN NEED OF IMPROVEMENT–SELECT NO MORE THAN 3 (APPROPRIATE IF MORE THAN ONE PERSON WILL BE INVOLVED) AND USE THE ASSESSMENT TABLE TO DISCUSS THE PRACTICES AND YOUR ASSESSMENT WITH THE COMMUNITY.

PART 3–NEGOTIATION /COUNSELING SESSION WITH THE INTERVENTION TRIAL COMMUNITY:

Let’s shift the conversation and talk more about the purpose of our study. Bats have proven to be important members of our ecosystem. As you know, their guano makes good fertilizer and they are the source of income for bat guano producing households. However, bats can carry diseases that can infect humans and other animals. To avoid illness outbreaks, people need to take basic precautions and learn to live safely with bats.

The practices that should be done to protect the family include:

1. Eliminate all direct exposure to bat guano and guano dust by always wearing full protective gear and clothing every time you work with bats or guano. The clothing, boots and gloves should not come into the house but stay safely stored outside in a designated area. And all protective clothing and gear should be washed or disinfected between uses.
2. To avoid spreading any possible contamination, hands must be washed with soap or detergent and water after any work with bats or guano and after all PPE has been removed.
3. All bat guano being stored should not be near the house and should be secured from animals in a plastic bag.

In our discussion earlier we found that: [Interviewer needs to make a judgment about observations and discuss each of these with community members present.]

Practice	Excellent (behavior is optimal)	Good (most of the behavior is suboptimal)	Poor (not observing the practice, or doing it poorly or occasionally)
Wearing full PPE for tasks with bats or guano			
Cleaning PPE appropriately			
Washing hands with soap/detergent after contact with bats or guano			

Based on this review, you could do more to protect your family by: [Pick two-three areas—no more than 3—where the family could do better to protect themselves. And explain this to the participant(s)]

1. Practice: _____
Person: _____
2. Practice: _____
Person: _____
3. Practice: _____
Person: _____

ASK

- Do you agree with this assessment of where you and your family's practices are protective and where they could be better to give you more security? ___Y/N Why?
- Would you be willing to try some things to improve your security? I will explain them and then ask you about your thoughts.
- Interviewer: Based on the trials that the family member (s) might try, pick the negotiation sheet for intervention trials that correspond to the practices the participants should focus on.
- Proceed the community with each intervention trial. Talk to the community selected for the intervention trials not a proxy.
 - a. share the best / suboptimal practice with the community using the guide. Check their understanding.
 - b. For each practice complete the following:

Intervention I: Trial _____

- As I described this practice to you, what is your reaction?
- Is it something you(and/or members of your family) can do?
- Can you do it routinely?
- Can you describe to me how you would do it?
- Will you be able to get, or do you have, what you need for the practice (PPE, plastic bags, soap, covers for food, etc.)

NOTE: IF THERE ARE THINGS THAT THE PARTICIPANT FEELS THEY CANNOT GET SUCH AS RUBBER BOOTS LOOK AT THE OPTIONS OFFERED IN THE GUIDE AND NEGOTIATE ALTERNATIVES WITH THEM. WHAT CAN THEY DO TO GET CLOSE TO THE OPTIMAL BEHAVIOR.

- Are you willing to try to put this recommendation into practice for the next 2-3 weeks?
 - Y /N.
- If, yes, do you have any questions or concerns?
- If not, why not? (Try to respond to the person's concerns and see if you can get them to commit to trying.
- Will you talk about this with your family?
- Do you believe doing this will offer some protection from harm that bats might cause? ___Y/N and Why?

REMIND THEM THAT THIS IS JUST TRYING. THEY DON'T HAVE TO CONTINUE THE PRACTICE AFTER THE TRIAL IS THEY DON'T WANT TO.

Intervention 2: Trial

- As I described this practice to you, what is your reaction?
- Is it something you (and/or members of your family) can do?
- Can you do it routinely?
- Can you describe to me how you would do it?
- Will you be able to get, or do you have, what you need for the practice (PPE, plastic bags, soap, covers for food, etc.)

NOTE: IF THERE ARE THINGS THAT THE PARTICIPANT FEELS THEY CANNOT GET SUCH AS RUBBER BOOTS LOOK AT THE OPTIONS OFFERED IN THE GUIDE AND NEGOTIATE ALTERNATIVES WITH THEM. WHAT CAN THEY DO TO GET CLOSE TO THE OPTIMAL BEHAVIOR.

- Are you willing to try to put this recommendation into practice for the next 2-3 weeks?
 - Y /N.
- If, yes, Do you have any questions or concerns?
- If not, why not? (Try to respond to the person's concerns and see if you can get them to commit to trying.
- Will you talk about this with your family?
- Do you believe doing this will offer some protection from harm that bats might cause?
___Y/N and Why?

REMINDE THEM THAT THIS IS JUST TRYING. THEY DON'T HAVE TO CONTINUE THE PRACTICE AFTER THE TRIAL IS THEY DON'T WANT TO.

CLOSURE:

Thank you for spending this time to talk about how to protect your family and for agreeing to try a few simple things that should make a difference for your family.

Either I, or another person from the project will come back to see how you are doing with the practice. We want to learn what goes well and where there are difficulties. We would like to make this something everyone can do.

Before I leave, can you tell me again what you are going to try over these next weeks?

Note how s/he explains the practices:

Thank the participant.

Annex 5: Midpoint Consultative Dialogue

INTERVIEW GUIDE—MIDPOINT VISIT

SAME for CBGHC in KAMPOT AND BATTAMBANG

General Information:

CBGHC's ID: _____

Note:

- Please be sure to interview the CBGHC who agreed to each intervention trial during the community dialogues and intervention kickoff.
- Mention to them that our main purpose is to learn from them about the suggestions that they agreed to try. We do not want to promote actions essential for the reduction of bat-borne disease and risk of viral spillover from bats to humans without understanding the benefits and obstacles that people face in trying to follow them.

Name of interviewer: _____

Date of visit: _____ / _____ / _____ (dd/mm/yyyy), Time (start-end) _____

TRIALS Household agreed to and the person who agreed.

Note: Complete before interview and fill in spaces in the guide below

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____

QUESTIONS

Before we talk about the specific practices that you are trying, I have a few questions:

1. Following our first visit and your agreement to try certain new or modified practices, did you discuss your agreements with others in the family?

Yes, which ones?

No

2. Are the people that you talked to about the practice also going to have to follow the practice?

Yes, what were their reactions?

No, what were their comments / what were they curious about?

Now let's talk about the different practices you are trying:

Use the list of intervention trials that each community member agreed to implement since the community dialogue and intervention kickoff, and ask them the key reminder questions and counselling activities as below:

Intervention

1: _____

Reminder: Are you talking to the right person?

1. Have you tried this practice or done anything to be able to implement it?

Yes, what are your practices?

No, what was the reason?

What can motivate you to start the intervention trials agreed?

2. Is the practice according to the agreement? (Look at your reminder card for this intervention trial and also check the reminder sheet that the participant might have filled out. Take a picture of the participant's reminder sheet)

Sub-activities of intervention trials	Responses		Observed		List down their practices
	Yes	No	Yes	No	

3. What would you do with your trials in the remaining trial periods (until 2 June)?

4. Do you have questions or suggestions related to starting or continuing your intervention trial?

Yes No

If yes, what are they?

Intervention

2: _____

Reminder: Are you talking to the right person for this trial?

1. Have you tried this practice or done anything to be able to implement it?

- Yes, what are your practices?
- No, what was the reason?

What can motivate you to start the intervention trial agreed?

2. Is the practice according to the agreement? (Look at your reminder card for this intervention trial and also check the reminder sheet that the participant might have filled out. Take a picture of the participant's reminder sheet)

Sub-activities of trials	Responses		Observed		List down their practices
	Yes	No	Yes	No	

3. What will you do with your trials in the remaining trial periods (until 2 June)?

4. Do you have questions or suggestions related to starting or continuing your intervention trial?

Yes No

If yes, what are they?

Reminder: Are you talking to the right person for this trial?

1. Have you tried this practice or done anything to be able to implement it?

- Yes, what are your practices?
- No, what was the reason?

What can motivate you to start the trial agreed?

2. Is the practice according to the agreement? (Look at your reminder card for this trial and also check the reminder sheet that the participant might have filled out. Take a picture of the participant’s reminder sheet)

Sub-activities of trials	Responses		Observed		List down their practices
	Yes	No	Yes	No	

3. What will you do with your trials in the remaining trial periods (until 2 June)?
4. Do you have questions or suggestions related to starting or continuing your intervention trial?
- Yes No
- If yes, what are they?
-

CLOSURE:

Remind the person of what they have accomplished.

Confirm those parts of the practice or the entire practice that they will do in the coming week or period of the trial.

Tell them that you intend to follow-up with them again at the end of August as the final visit.

Thank the person for participating in the trial to improve ways that people can live safely with bats.

Annex 6: Final Consultative Dialogue

INTERVIEW GUIDE—FINAL COMMUNITY VISIT

[SAME for CBGHC in BTB AND KPT]

CBGHC's ID: _____

Note: might want to interview more than one person in the community depending on intervention trials

Name of interviewer: _____

Date of visit ___ / ___ / ____ (dd/mm/yyyy), Time: _____

Intervention trial community members agreed to: (complete before interview and fill in spaces in the guide below and note any commitments made at the mid-check)

1. _____ | mid-check: _____
2. _____ | mid-check: _____
3. _____ | mid-check: _____

Greetings and introductions:

Purpose of visit—to discuss the complete experience of the trial and to learn from the person about whether or not the changes have made a difference in the routine of their guano business or of living safely with bats.

To learn the advantages and disadvantages experienced with the new practice and whether it is something to recommend to others.

It is important to be honest about the experience.

Review the practices that the farmer or key person agreed to try based on the first interview.

QUESTIONS

Before we talk about the specific practices that you agreed try, I have a few questions:

1. Since my first visit have you discussed / consulted with others in the family about the practices?
 - Yes, which ones?
 - How many times did you talk to them?
 - What was/were the discussions or consultations about?
 - No
2. Since my first visit have you discussed / consulted with others outside of the family about any practice?

Note: does not include the mid-check

 - Yes, with who?
 - What was/were the discussions about?
 - No

Now let's talk about the different practices you are trying:

Based on each practice the community members agreed to try, ask the questions listed. Probe for reasons why and make detailed notes.

Intervention Trial 01 _____

1. **Note:** check where the family was during the mid-term check-in

If they had not started, did you start this practice?

- No, what are the reasons? Probe why?
- Yes
 - If they started but had more things to do or improve, were you able to make any of the changes we discussed since my last visit? Yes No
 - What have you done since my last visit?
 - If they were doing the practice well, did you continue the practice since my last visit?

2. Let's review exactly what you have been doing—how you have implemented the practices?

Is the practice according to the agreement?

Sub-activities of trials	Responses		Observation		List down if any of their practices was changes/adjusted
	Yes	No	Yes	No	

3. If the practice changed what did the person do and why?

4. OBSERVE as much as possible. For example, the storage place for the guano, the handwashing facility for the presence of soap or detergent, where PPE is stored:

Note:

- a. If there can be a quantitative measure, ask about it, for example how many dead bats did you find and dispose of? Or how many days this week did you harvest guano using full PPE?
- b. Take a picture or collect the reminder sheets if they will give them to you so that we have any quantitative information that is available.

5. What are your thoughts related to this practice?

Probes to use: Has it been easy? Are the costs incurred manageable? What do others in the household think?

- Positive reactions:
- Negative reactions:

6. Will you continue with the changes / with the practice? And why or why not?

- Continue, why?

- No continue, why?
- 7. If they have not completed the practice: Are you likely to take further steps to do this practice?
Note: Please note all steps here—for example each piece of PPE that they might be using or using properly
 - Yes, why?
 - No, why?
- 8. Are you likely to recommend this practice to others? Why / why not?
 - Yes, why? How would you convince them to try it (please specify the exact words)?
 - No, why?

Intervention Trial 02

1. **Note:** check where the family was during the mid-term check-in

If they had not started, did you start this practice?

- No, what are the reasons? Probe why?
- Yes
 - If they started but had more things to do or improve, were you able to make any of the changes we discussed since my last visit? Yes No
 - What have you done since my last visit?
 - If they were doing the practice well, did you continue the practice since my last visit?

2. Let's review exactly what you have been doing—how you have implemented the practices?

Is the practice according to the agreement?

Sub-activities of trials	Responses		Observation		List down if any of their practices was changes/adjusted
	Yes	No	Yes	No	

3. If the practice changed what did the person do and why?
4. **OBSERVE** as much as possible. For example, the storage place for the guano, the handwashing facility for the presence of soap, where PPE is stored:
- Note:
- b. If there can be a quantitative measure, ask about it, for example how many dead bats did you find and dispose of? Or how many days this week did you harvest guano using full PPE?
 - c. Take a picture or collect the reminder sheets if they will give them to you so that we have any quantitative information that is available.

5. What are your thoughts related to this practice?

Probes to use: Has it been easy? Are the costs incurred manageable? What do others in the household think?

- Positive reactions:
- Negative reactions:

6. Will you continue with the changes / with the practice? And why or why not?

- Continue, why?
- No continue, why?

7. If have not completed the practice: Are you likely to take further steps to do this practice?

Note: Please note all steps here—for example each piece of PPE that they might be using or using properly

- Yes, why?
- No, why?

8. Are you likely to recommend this practice to others? Why / why not?

- Yes, why? How would you convince them to try it (please specify the exact words)?
- No, why?

CLOSURE:

- Finally, in our first discussion I asked you about your feeling of risk or danger in the work that you do with bats or even living in close proximity with bats. After implementing these particular practices, please tell me how you feel.
- On a scale of 1-10 with 10 being high risk/danger and 1 being the lowest risk /danger:

How do you feel about your personal risk?

Explain:

How do you feel about your family's risk / danger?

Explain:

- Is there any one of these practices that shifted your feeling?
- Remind the person of what they have accomplished.
- Thank the person for participating in the trial to improve ways that people can live safely with bats.

Annex 7: IRB 394 NECHR

ក្រសួងសុខាភិបាល
MINISTRY OF HEALTH
គណៈកម្មាធិការជាតិរៀបចំការស្រាវជ្រាវសុខាភិបាល
National Ethics Committee for Health Research

Nº 394 NECHR

ព្រះរាជាណាចក្រកម្ពុជា
KINGDOM OF CAMBODIA
ជាតិ សាសនា ព្រះមហាក្សត្រ
NATION RELIGION KING

Phnom Penh, December 29, 2023

Dr. Hellen Amuguni

Project: Community-level risk reduction interventions. Version N° 1, dated 08th December 2023.

Reference: 22nd December 2023 NECHR meeting minutes

Dear Dr. Hellen Amuguni,

I am pleased to notify you that your study protocol entitled “Community-level risk reduction interventions. Version N° 1, dated 08th December 2023” has been approved by National Ethics Committee for Health Research (NECHR) in the meeting on 22nd December 2023. This approval is valid for twelve months after the approval date.

NECHR also wish to remind the Principal Investigator that all research activities to be conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic must strictly follow the latest prevention measures set by the MOH and the relevant local authorities.

The Principal Investigator of the project shall submit following document to the committee’s secretariat at the National Institute of Public Health at #80, Samdach Penn Nouth Blvd (289), Sangkat Boeungkok 2, Khan Tuol Kork, Phnom Penh. (Tel: 012 528 789, 086 762 113, 012 203 382. Email: nouthsarida@gmail.com, cheatasoft27@gmail.com):

- Annual progress report
- Final scientific report
- Patient/participant feedback (if any)
- Analyzing serious adverse events report (if applicable)

The Principal Investigator should be aware that there might be site monitoring visits at any time from NECHR team during the project implementation and should provide full cooperation to the team.

Regards,
 Chairman

Prof. ENG HUOT

**National Ethics Committee
 for Health Research
 (NECHR)**

ឡូត៍លេខ៨០, វិថីសម្តេច ប៉ែន នុត (២៨៩) សង្កាត់បឹងកក់ ២, ខណ្ឌ ទួលគោក, រាជធានីភ្នំពេញ, ខ្មែរស៊ីហ្គេត(៨៥៥-០១២) ៨៤២ ៨៤២, (៨៥៥-០១២) ៨២៨ ៧៨៩, (៨៥៥-០១២) ២០៣ ៣៨២
 Lot #80, Samdach Penn Nouth Blvd (289), Sangkat Boeung Kok 2, Khan Tuol Kork, Phnom Penh, Cambodia. Tel: (855-012) 842 442, (855-012) 528 789, (855-012) 203 382

Annex 8: Photos from the Events

PHOTO 1. Pictorial lectures on zoonotic diseases and biosafety measures for the community members of PRSSFPC in Battambang province.

PHOTO 2. Seven infographics on zoonotic diseases and hygiene practices, explained and guided by the Technical Officials of Cambodia CDC.

PHOTO 3. OH-DREAM WG members conducted the market surveys on PPE availability and prices in local markets in Banan district.

PHOTO 4. Pictorial lectures and infographics on zoonotic diseases and biosafety measures for the community members of PRSSFPC and their hand-raising as self-selection for implementing the interventions in Kampot province.

PHOTO 5. One of OH-DREAM WG members conducted a midpoint/follow-up assessment with the group of female guano harvesters in Kampot province.

PHOTO 6. A group photo of the committed participants in PKLFPC who implemented the co-designed risk reduction interventions in Kampot province.

PHOTO 7. Practices of the use of PPE among the committed participants while preparing their collected bat guano for sales to their traders-cum-transporters in Kampot province.

PHOTO 8. A renovation of pre-existing handwashing station by refilling with water, a supply of detergent holder and detergent and the practice of handwashing after harvesting the guano in Kampot province.